

Synthesis and Characterization of Complexes of Co(II), Cu(II), Cd(II), Mg(II) with Disubstituted Thioureas

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N-2-(6-methyl substituted pyridyl)-N'-substituted thioureas, N-2-(5-chloro substituted pyridyl)-N'-substituted thiourea and N- α -naphthyl-N'-substituted thiourea and their Co(II), Cu(II), Cd(II) and Hg(II) complexes were synthesized and characterized by elemental analysis. (The metals were estimated by atomic absorption spectrophotometer). Molar conductance, ir, uv and magnetic measurements were made.

TRANSITION metal complexes of substituted thioureas have been studied by several workers¹⁻⁵ but no work has been reported on Co(II), Cu(II), Cd(II), Hg(II) chloride complexes of N-2-(6-methyl substituted pyridyl)-N'-substituted thioureas, N-2-(5-chloro substituted pyridyl)-N'-substituted thiourea and N- α -naphthyl-N'-substituted thiourea. The present communication reports an attempt to study the Co(II), Cu(II), Cd(II) and Hg(II) complexes of these disubstituted thioureas.

Experimental

Chemicals: All chemicals used were of B. D. H. 'AnalaR', E. Merck 'GR' quality. 6-Methyl-2-aminopyridine and α -naphthyl amine used were obtained from Sigma R Chemicals and Riedel-Haen, respectively.

Apparatus: Atomic absorption studies were performed on Perkin-Elmer-306, atomic absorption spectrophotometer. Melting points were recorded in capillary melting point apparatus (Arthur H. Thomas Co.). Conductance measurements were taken on a conductivity meter (Toshniwal, India) with dipping electrode cell. IR spectra were recorded on model 577 Perkin-Elmer IR spectrophotometer in nujol mull and uv spectra on Hitachi spectrophotometer, model 139. Magnetic measurements were performed on Gouy's balance.

Synthesis of mustard oil (isothiocyanate): Synthesis of phenyl isothiocyanate was done by the method described by Vogel⁷. Allyl isothiocyanate and methyl isothiocyanate were synthesized by similar method except that the amines used were allyl amine and methyl amine respectively in place of aniline.

Synthesis of 5-chloro-2-amino-pyridine: The compound was prepared by the method described by Shozo Shibata *et al*⁸.

Synthesis of N-2-(6-methyl substituted pyridyl)-N'-substituted thioureas, N-2-(5-chloro substituted pyridyl)-N'-substituted thiourea and N- α -naphthyl-N'-substituted thiourea: Equimolar amounts of amino compounds and mustard oil (isothiocyanate) were

taken in ethanol. The mixture was refluxed for about 1-2 hr. The solution was then kept in ice-cold water for some time when substituted thiourea precipitated out as fine crystals. The precipitate was filtered and washed with ethanol and finally recrystallised from ethanol and dried in a vacuum desiccator.

In the case of 2-amino-5-chloro-pyridine, the substituted thiourea was subjected to charcoal treatment in benzene to remove the colouring material and finally recrystallised from C₆H₆ and dried in a vacuum desiccator.

The formation of the substituted thioureas can be represented by the following equations:

Preparation of complexes: 0.01 Mole of CoCl₂·6H₂O, CuCl₂·2H₂O, HgCl₂ (all B. D. H. "AnalaR") or CdCl₂ (E. Merck 'GR') in *n*-butanol or ethyl alcohol was added slowly to a hot solution of 0.025 mole of the ligand in the same solvent. In the case of Co(II), the reaction mixture was refluxed for 30 to 60 min. Later, 50 to 60% solvent was evaporated. The crystallization was achieved by keeping this concentrated solution in ice-cold water for some time. Blue or bluish green crystals separated out.

Copper(II) complexes immediately precipitated out as white crystals from ethanol solution which suggests that copper(II) gets reduced to copper(I) state. In the case of mercury(II), no precipitation was obtained till the concentration ratio of metal/

ligand was raised to 1 : 1. This metal/ligand ratio resulted only in milky coloured reaction mixture which gave white crystals when kept for some time. Excess of metal chloride immediately gave white precipitate.

Cadmium(II) complexes required more vigorous condition such as metal/ligand ratio of 1 : 1 with continuous stirring in hot condition for 30-60 min followed by a precipitation time of 10-12 hr at low temperature. The complexes thus obtained were white in colour.

These complexes could not be recrystallised either from *n*-butanol or ethanol. Therefore, to ensure purity, they were washed several times with the solvent followed by 2 or 3 washings with ether (10 ml each time) and dried in vacuum.

Results and Discussion

The elemental analysis of these complexes indicates that they are formed in 1 : 2 (M : L) ratio (where L=substituted thiourea) except when N-allyl-N'- α -naphthyl thiourea is used as ligand, in which case they are in 1 : 1 (M : L) ratio. The melting points range from 152°-260° with decomposition.

The molar conductance of these complexes in DMF were found to be quite low. 1 : 1 Electrolytes generally have conductance in the range 70-110 mhos^o, showing the non-electrolytic nature of the complexes. Thus, the chlorine atoms can be considered to be coordinated to the metal ion and are not present as chloride ions. The values obtained in the present work are indicative of an octahedral geometry for these Co(II) complexes. Complexes of the other metals are diamagnetic in nature.

The uv spectra (CHCl₃) of these complexes exhibited two intense absorption maxima in the region of 260-280 nm and 300-310 nm, (except in the case of N-allyl-N'- α -naphthyl thiourea which showed only one thiocarbonyl π - π^* transition). These transition bands have been assigned to thiocarbonyl π - π^* and pyridyl π - π^* transitions^{9,10}.

All the uv spectra of the complexes were compared with uv spectra of ligands. The absorption maxima showed an erratic shift to lower or higher wave length of about 10 nm or in some cases no shift in any appreciable amount in wave length. The intensity of the absorption of complexes was higher than that of ligands. Out of the two absorption maxima, the π - π^* transition of thiocarbonyl (C=S) showed strongest interaction in metal complexes when compared with ligands.

The ir spectra of the ligands are complex and only the peaks which can be assigned with reasonable certainty are presented. From the point of view of ascertaining the donar sites of the ligands the following peaks are important: ν (C=C+C=N) (1630-1590 cm⁻¹)¹⁻⁴; τ_B (NCN)+ ν (NCN+C=S)

(1060-1010 cm⁻¹)^{1-4,11} and ν (C=S) (741-722 cm⁻¹)^{1-4,12}. The ν (C=C+C=N) band at 1630 cm⁻¹ has been reported to be shifted in the case of coordinated pyridyl nitrogen¹³. The behaviour of this band is of considerable importance in deciding whether the heterocyclic nitrogen is involved in the coordination with metal. In the case of the present complexes, this band shifted to higher or lower frequencies in an irregular fashion thereby precluding any unambiguous assertion of metal ligand bonding through the pyridyl nitrogen (except for N-allyl-N'- α -naphthyl thiourea).

The band appearing at 1060-1010 cm⁻¹ in the ligand and assigned to ν (C=C+C=S) mode, was reduced in its intensity or shifted to lower frequencies in most of the spectra of the complexes.

The mode ν (C=S), occurring at 741-722 cm⁻¹, was shifted to slight higher frequencies in metal complexes in the case of 6-methyl-pyridyl substituted thiourea ligands, while in the other complexes it was found to be reduced in intensity or shifted to lower frequencies. The shift to slight higher frequencies may be accounted for substitution effect in 6-position of pyridyl ring.

The shifting of the bands assigned to ν (NCN+C=S) and ν (C=S) mode to lower frequency (in some cases change to higher frequencies) or reduction of their intensities in metal complexes may be due to the sulphur metal coordination bond formation¹⁻⁴.

One more possible site for the coordination between metal and ligand may be one of the nitrogens of substituted thiourea unit. If this nitrogen and sulphur act as donors, a four membered chelate ring would be formed which is quite unstable in comparison to the 6-membered chelate ring formed by the donation of electrons from the nitrogen of pyridine ring and the thiocarbonyl sulphur.

From these studies of eighteen complexes of Co(II), Cu(II), Cd(II) and Hg(II), it can be reasonably concluded that complexes formed are non-electrolytes with 1 : 2 metal to ligand ratio except in the case of N-allyl-N'- α -naphthyl thiourea where the ratio is 1 : 1. The chlorine in the complexes appears to be present in the inner sphere of the complexes. On the basis of these measurements, the following structures of the complex can be assigned.

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